

AJRALGAN YADROLI UCH O'ZGARUVCHILI FUNKSIYALAR UCHUN XUSUSIY INTEGRAL TENGLAMALARNI YECHISH

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada yadrolari ajralgan ko'rinishga ega bo'lgan uch o'zgaruvchili funksiyalar uchun chiziqli xususiy integral tenglamani yechish masalasi o'rganilgan. $C[a,b]^3$ fazoda qaralayotgan tenglama uchun yagona uzluksiz yechimning mavjudligi va yagonaligi isbotlangan. Yadrolar ajralgan holda berilganda, masala bir o'zgaruvchili Fredgolm integral tenglamasiga keltirilishi ko'rsatilgan va yechim aniq formulalar orqali ifodalangan. Bundan tashqari, bir jinsli tenglamaning nolmas yechimga ega bo'lish sharti aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: xususiy integral tenglama, ajralgan yadro, Fredgolm integral tenglamasi, uch o'zgaruvchili funksiya, yagona yechim, bir jinsli tenglama, $C[a,b]^3$ fazosi.

РЕШЕНИЕ ЧАСТНЫХ ИНТЕГРАЛЬНЫХ УРАВНЕНИЙ ДЛЯ ФУНКЦИЙ ТРЁХ ПЕРЕМЕННЫХ С ВЫРОЖДЕННЫМИ ЯДРАМИ

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется задача решения линейного частно-интегрального уравнения для функций трёх переменных с вырожденными ядрами. В пространстве $C[a,b]^3$ доказаны существование и единственность непрерывного решения рассматриваемого уравнения. Показано, что при вырожденных ядрах задача сводится к интегральному уравнению Фредгольма одной переменной, а решение выражается в явном виде через точные формулы. Также установлено условие существования ненулевого решения однородного уравнения.

Ключевые слова: частно-интегральное уравнение, вырожденное ядро, интегральное уравнение Фредгольма, функция трёх переменных, единственность решения, однородное уравнение, пространство $C[a,b]^3$.

SOLVING PARTIAL INTEGRAL EQUATIONS FOR FUNCTIONS OF THREE VARIABLES WITH DEGENERATE KERNELS

Abstract: This paper investigates the problem of solving a linear partial integral equation for functions of three variables with degenerate (separated) kernels. The existence and uniqueness of a continuous solution in the space $C[a,b]^3$ are proved. It is shown that when the kernels are given in separated form, the problem reduces to a single-variable Fredholm integral equation of the second kind, and the solution is expressed explicitly through exact formulas. Additionally, the condition for the homogeneous equation to possess a nontrivial solution is established.

Keywords: partial integral equation, degenerate kernel, Fredholm integral equation, function of three variables, uniqueness of solution, homogeneous equation, $C[a,b]^3$ space.

Ushbu maqolada biz uch o'zgaruvchili funksiyalar uchun chiziqli xususiy integral tenglamani yechish masalasini keltiramiz:

$$\varphi(x, y, z) + \int_a^b K(x, t)\varphi(t, y, z) dt + \int_a^b N(y, t)\varphi(x, t, z) dt + i + \int_a^b M(z, t)\varphi(x, y, t) dt = f(x, y, z) \quad (1)$$

Mos bir jinsli xususiy integral tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishdadir:

$$\varphi(x, y, z) + \int_a^b K(x, t)\varphi(t, y, z) dt + \int_a^b N(y, t)\varphi(x, t, z) dt + i + \int_a^b M(z, t)\varphi(x, y, t) dt = 0 \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda $K(x,t)$, $N(y,t)$, $M(z,t)$ va $f(x,y,z)$ – mos ravishda $[a,b]^2$ va $[a,b]^3$ sohalarida aniqlangan uzluksiz funksiyalar; φ – izlanayotgan nomalum funksiya.

Ushbu maqolada (1) tenglamaning yechimini $C[a,b]^3$ fazoda qaraymiz va quyidagi teoremani isbotlaymiz.

1-Teorema. Faraz qilaylik, $K(x,t) = \psi_1(x)\hat{\psi}_1(t)$, $N(y,t) = \psi_2(y)\hat{\psi}_2(t)$,

$$M(z, t) = \psi_3(z)\hat{\psi}_3(t) \text{ u } d_i = 1 + \int_a^b \psi_i(t)\hat{\psi}_i(t) dt \neq 0, i = 1, 2, 3;$$

$$\Delta_\alpha = d_\beta + d_\gamma - 1 \neq 0, \alpha \neq \beta \neq \gamma, \alpha = 1, 2, 3;$$

a) agar $\Delta = d_1 + d_2 + d_3 - 2 \neq 0$, sharti bajarilsa, u holda (1) chizikli integral tenglama quyidagi formula bilan ifodalanuvchi yagona uzluksiz yechimga ega bo'ladi:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x, y, z) = f(x, y, z) - \int_a^b \left\{ \frac{K(x, t)f(t, y, z)}{d_1} + \frac{N(y, t)f(x, t, z)}{d_2} + \frac{M(z, t)f(x, y, t)}{d_3} \right\} dt \\ + \int_a^b \int_a^b \left\{ \frac{d_1 + d_2}{d_1 d_2 \Delta_3} K(x, t_1) N(y, t_2) f(t_1, t_2, z) + \frac{d_1 + d_3}{d_1 d_3 \Delta_2} K(x, t_1) M(z, t_2) f(t_1, y, t_2) + \frac{d_2 + d_3}{d_2 d_3 \Delta_1} N(y, t_1) M(z, t_2) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{C}{(d_1 d_2 d_3)^2 \Delta \Delta_1 \Delta_2 \Delta_3} \int_a^b \int_a^b \int_a^b K(x, t_1) N(y, t_2) \times \right. \\ \left. \times M(z, t_3) f(t_1, t_2, t_3) dt_1 dt_2 dt_3, \right. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Bu yerda

$$\begin{aligned} C = -(1 + \Delta) i \\ \times (\Delta_1 \Delta_2 + \Delta_1 \Delta_3 + \Delta_2 \Delta_3) i - (d_1 d_2 \Delta_3 + d_1 d_3 \Delta_2 + d_2 d_3 \Delta_1 + d_1 d_2 d_3) \times \\ \times [d_1 d_2 d_3 \Delta - (d_1 - 1)(d_2 - 1)(d_3 - 1)(1 + \Delta)]; \end{aligned}$$

b) agar $\Delta = d_1 + d_2 + d_3 - 2 = 0$, bo'lsa, u holda (2) bir jinsli integral tenglama nolga teng bo'lmagan (trivial bo'lmagan) yechimga ega bo'ladi.

Teoremani isbotlashda, $K(x,t) = \psi_1(x)\hat{\psi}_1(t)$, $N(y,t) = \psi_2(y)\hat{\psi}_2(t)$, $M(z,t) = \psi_3(z)\hat{\psi}_3(t)$, bo'lsin deb faraz qilinadi (ya'ni yadrolar ayrilgan ko'rinishga ega). U holda (2.1) tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishni oladi:

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(x, y, z) + \psi_1(x) \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_1(t)\varphi(t, y, z) dt + \psi_2(y) \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_2(t)\varphi(x, t, z) dt + i \\ + \psi_3(z) \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_3(t)\varphi(x, y, t) dt = f(x, y, z). \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Deb hisoblab $\int_a^b \hat{\psi}_2(t) \varphi(x, t, z) dt$ va $\int_a^b \hat{\psi}_3(t) \varphi(x, y, t) dt$ (4) tenglamadagi ma'lum

ifodalarni hisobga olgan holda, xususiy integral tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$\varphi(x, y, z) + \psi_1(x) \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_1(t) \varphi(t, y, z) dt = f_1(x, y, z). \quad (5)$$

Bu yerda

$$f_1(x, y, z) = f(x, y, z) - \psi_2(y) \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_2(t) \varphi(x, t, z) dt - \psi_3(z) \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_3(t) \varphi(x, y, t) dt. \quad (6)$$

y va z o'zgaruvchilarini tayinlangan (fiksirlangan) deb hisoblab, (5) tenglamani quyidagi ko'rinishga keltirish mumkin:

$$\varphi_{yz}(x) + \psi_1(x) \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_1(t) \varphi_{yz}(t) dt = f_{1yz}(x) \quad (7)$$

(7) tenglama ikkinchi turdagi Fredgolm chiziqli integral tenglamasidir. Ushbu tenglamaning yadrosi ajralgan bo'lib, uning rangi birga teng. Ma'lumki, bunday ko'rinishdagi tenglamalar oson yechiladi.

1-lemma. Agar $K(x, t) = \psi_1(x) \hat{\psi}_1(t)$, $N(y, t) = \psi_2(y) \hat{\psi}_2(t)$,

$$M(z, t) = \psi_3(z) \hat{\psi}_3(t), \quad d_i = \int_a^b \psi_i(t) \hat{\psi}_i(t) dt \neq 0, \quad i=1,2,3, \quad \Delta_\alpha = d_\beta + d_\gamma - 1 \neq 0,$$

$\alpha \neq \beta \neq \gamma$, $\alpha=1,2,3$ bo'lsa, u holda (2.2) bir jinsli tenglama va

$$\varphi(x, y, z) = \frac{(1-d_1-d_2-d_3)\psi_1(x)\psi_2(y)\psi_3(z)}{\Delta_1\Delta_2\Delta_3} \int_a^b \int_a^b \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_1(t_1)\hat{\psi}_2(t_2)\hat{\psi}_3(t_3) \times \\ \times \varphi(t_1, t_2, t_3) dt_1 dt_2 dt_3 \quad (8)$$

o'zaro ekvivalentdir.

Lemmaning isboti teorema birinchi qismining isbotlash jarayonini (2) tenglamaga nisbatan takrorlashdan kelib chiqadi. Haqiqatan ham, $f(x, y, z) = 0$ bo'lganda ushbu jarayonni takrorlab, uch o'zgaruvchili funksiyali, ayniy yadroli (8) bir jinsli Fredgolm integral tenglamasiga kelamiz.

b) Endi teoremaning ikkinchi qismini isbotlashda Fredgolm teoremasiga ko'ra, $d_1 + d_2 + d_3 - 2 = 0$ sharti bajarilganda (8) tenglama **nolmas** (noldan farqli) **yechimga ega** deb faraz qilib,

$$C = \frac{(1-d_1-d_2-d_3)}{\Delta_1\Delta_2\Delta_3} \int_a^b \int_a^b \int_a^b \hat{\psi}_1(t_1)\hat{\psi}_2(t_2)\hat{\psi}_3(t_3) \varphi(t_1, t_2, t_3) dt_1 dt_2 dt_3$$

$\varphi(x, y, z) = C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z)$ ga ega bo'lamiz. $\varphi(x, y, z)$ ning ushbu ifodasini (2) tenglamaga qo'yib, quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z) + C \psi_1(x) \int_a^b \psi_1(t_1) \hat{\psi}_1(t_1) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z) dt + \dots$$

$$+C \psi_2(y) \int_a^b \psi_2(t_2) \hat{\psi}_2(t_2) \psi_1(x) \psi_3(z) dt + C \psi_3(z) \int_a^b \psi_3(t_3) \hat{\psi}_3(t_3) \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) dt = 0$$

Bundan

$$C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z) + C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z) (d_1 - 1) + C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z) (d_2 - 1) + i + C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z) (d_3 - 1) = C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z) (1 + d_1 - 1 + d_2 - 1 + d_3 - 1) = 0$$

yoki

$$C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z) (d_1 + d_2 + d_3 - 2) = 0.$$

Demak, teorema shartiga ko'ra $(d_1 + d_2 + d_3 - 2) = 0$ bo'lganligi sababli, $\varphi(x, y, z) = C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z)$ funksiya (2.2) bir jinsli tenglamaning nolmas yechimidir. Ya'ni, 1-lemmaning asosida $\varphi(x, y, z) = C \psi_1(x) \psi_2(y) \psi_3(z)$ funksiya (8) tenglamaning uzluksiz yechimi hisoblanadi. Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqqan holda teoremani to'liq isbotlashga erishiladi.

Yuqoridagi teoremadan $f \equiv 0$ holati uchun quyidagi natija bevosita kelib chiqadi.

Natija. Agar $K(x, t) = \psi_1(x) \hat{\psi}_1(t)$, $N(y, t) = \psi_2(y) \hat{\psi}_2(t)$,

$M(z, t) = \psi_3(z) \hat{\psi}_3(t)$ bo'lib, $d_i = 1 + \int_a^b \psi_i(t) \hat{\psi}_i(t) dt \neq 0, i=1,2,3$; $\Delta_\alpha = d_\beta + d_\gamma - 1 \neq 0$,

$\alpha \neq \beta \neq \gamma, \alpha=1,2,3$ va $\Delta = d_1 + d_2 + d_3 - 2 \neq 0$, shartlar bajarilsa, u holda

$$\varphi(x, y, z) + \int_a^b K(x, t) \varphi(t, y, z) dt + \int_a^b N(y, t) \varphi(x, t, z) dt + i + \int_a^b M(z, t) \varphi(x, y, t) dt = 0 \quad (2)$$

bir jinsli tenglama faqat **trivial yechim** $\varphi(x, y, z) \equiv 0$ ga ega bo'ladi.

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